

ANTIFUNGAL ACTIVITIES OF *ALOE VERA* L. (*IN VIVO* & *IN VITRO* REGENERATED) WHOLE LEAF AND INNER GEL EXTRACTS

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ABSTRACT

The present study investigates the antifungal potential of *Aloe vera* L. whole leaf and inner gel extracts obtained from both *in vivo* grown and *in vitro* regenerated plants against clinically significant fungal pathogens. The selected fungal strains included *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Aspergillus fumigatus*, *Penicillium digitatum*, *Candida albicans*, and *Candida utilis*. Various solvent extracts, namely n-hexane, chloroform, ethyl acetate, methanol, and aqueous extracts, were prepared and evaluated using the disc diffusion method, while Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) was determined by agar dilution technique. The results demonstrated that all solvent extracts, except aqueous extracts, exhibited significant antifungal activity against the tested pathogens. Among them, ethyl acetate extracts showed the highest zone of inhibition, followed by methanol, chloroform, and n-hexane extracts.

Notably, extracts derived from *in vitro* regenerated plants, particularly inner gel extracts, displayed superior antifungal efficacy compared to *in vivo* samples. MIC analysis further confirmed that ethyl acetate extracts required the lowest concentration to inhibit fungal growth, indicating strong antifungal potency. The absence of activity in aqueous extracts suggests that bioactive antifungal compounds are more effectively extracted using organic solvents. The findings highlight the presence of potent phytochemicals in *Aloe vera* L. that contribute to its broad-spectrum antifungal activity. In conclusion, *Aloe vera* L. extracts,

especially ethyl acetate fractions of *in vitro* regenerated inner gel, demonstrate promising antifungal properties and may serve as a potential natural source for the development of antifungal therapeutics targeting human pathogenic fungi.

KEYWORDS: *Aloe vera* L., Antifungal activity, Phytochemicals, Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) and *In vitro* regeneration.

INTRODUCTION

In present investigation, number of fungal pathogens of clinical significance including *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Aspergillus fumigatus*, *Penicillium digitatum*, *Candida albicans* and *Candida utilis* were tested against different solvent extracts of *Aloe vera* L. (both *in vivo* grown and *in vitro* regenerated) whole leaf and inner gel, at the same time positive and negative controls were also taken to cross check the obtained results.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Preparation of crude extract

Leaves of the *Aloe vera* L. were collected from the already *in vitro* propagated and properly acclimatized 9-12 months old plants. *In vitro* propagation was the previous phase of our study to produce quality plant material to meet industrial requirement. Simultaneously leaves from 9-12 months old *in vivo* grown *Aloe vera* L. plants were also collected. Freshly collected *Aloe vera* L. leaves were washed with distilled water, followed by disinfecting with ethanol 70%. Later, in case of whole leaf crude extract preparation, leaves were chopped into the small pieces and were exposed to 50°C for 3 days to get dried. After complete drying, leaf parts were powdered using electric grinder, simultaneously in case of only gel crude extract preparation, upper green skin/rind of leaves was removed and latex was cut into small pieces and both types of leaf materials were homogenized separately. The homogenized materials were extracted with ethanol (95%). The ethanol from the extracted leaf materials was evaporated at 65°C temperature in water bath. The solvent was completely removed and dried to get powder. All the powdered plant materials including whole leaf and only gel were used for the preparation of aqueous and solvent extracts.

Aqueous extract

Extracts were prepared using the modified method of Case.^[1] 1:3 (w/v) ratios were used for the powdered leaf material and distilled water for extract preparation. The pulverized leaf material was used to prepare an infusion in hot (95°C) distilled water. The infusion was left

overnight under refrigeration (4°C) to prevent any possible contamination. After 24 h the extracts were kept in rotary shaker at 100 rpm for 1 h and filtered with Whatman No.1 filter paper and subsequently subjected to lyophilization at – 47.5°C. The frozen extract was then freeze dried to a powder, weighed, transferred into separate vial and preserved at 4°C for future analysis.

Solvent extracts

As in case of aqueous extract here also 1:3 (w/v) ratios were used for the powdered leaf material and different solvents for extract preparation. The pulverized leaves material was mixed with sufficient quantity of solvents viz., hexane, ethyl acetate, methanol and chloroform. It was kept in rotary shaker at 100 rpm overnight and filtered with Whatman No.1 filter paper and subsequently subjected to lyophilization at – 47.5°C. The dried extracts thus obtained was weighed, transferred into separate vials and preserved at 4°C for future analysis.

The antifungal activity of different extracts of *Aloe vera* L. (both *in vivo* grown and *in vitro* regenerated) whole leaf and inner gel were tested against number of fungal strains including *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Aspergillus fumigatus*, *Penicillium digitatum*, *Candida albicans* and *Candida utilis*. The fungal stock cultures were maintained on Sabouraud Dextrose Agar (SDA) and stored at 4°C.

Determination of antifungal potential of *Aloe vera* L.

Paper discs impregnated with specific antibiotics or the test substances were placed on the surface of the Sabouraud Dextrose Agar medium inoculated with the target organisms. The plates were incubated and the zones of inhibition around each disc were measured.

Sabouraud Dextrose Agar medium (SDA) was used for maintaining the fungal cultures. 47 g of Sabouraud dextrose agar medium (Hi Media) was suspended in 1000 ml of distilled water. The medium was dissolved completely by boiling and was then autoclaved at 15 lbs pressure (121°C, pH 5.6 ± 0.2) for 15 min.

5% Dimethyl Sulphoxide (DMSO) was used as negative control, while Ketoconazole and Fluconazole taken as standard positive controls and 0.5 McFarland opacity standard was also taken.

Assay

Antifungal activities of *Aloe vera* L. (both *in vivo* grown and *in vitro* regenerated) whole leaf and inner gel extracts were carried out by disc diffusion method using the Kirby-Bauer technique.^[2,3] All the fungal strains were maintained on Nutrient Agar (NA). Pure culture of fungal strains from the plate were inoculated onto SDA plate for sub culturing and kept at 25 °C for 72 h.

The inoculum was prepared by aseptically adding the fresh culture into 2 ml of sterile 0.145 mol/l saline tube and the cell density was adjusted to 0.5 McFarland turbidity standard to yield a microbial suspension of 1×10^6 CFU/ml. Standardized inoculum was transferred and spread evenly on SDA plates to yield a lawn culture. Sterile Whatmann No. 1 filter paper discs (5mm diameter) impregnated plant extracts (100 µg/disc) were placed on the inoculated SDA plates, and allowed to diffuse for half an hour at room temperature and then all the fungal strains containing plates were incubated at 25 °C. Disc containing 5% DMSO served as negative control whereas Ketoconazole and Fluconazole (100 µg/disc) served as positive control.

The plates were observed after 48h for the presence of inhibition of microbial growth that was indicated by the clear zone around the disc. The size of the zone of inhibition (including disc) was measured in millimeters. The absence of zone inhibition was interpreted as the absence of activity^[4,5]. All experiments were carried out in triplicates under strict aseptic conditions. The activities were expressed as resistant, if the zone of inhibition was less than 7 mm, intermediate (8-10 mm) and sensitive if more than 11 mm.^[6]

Determination of Minimum Inhibitory Concentrations (MIC)

MIC test was performed by Agar Dilution Method.^[7] Different concentrations of chloroform, methanol, ethyl acetate, *n*-hexane and aqueous extracts of *Aloe vera* L. (both *in vivo* grown and *in vitro* regenerated) whole leaf and inner gel from 0.125 to 16 mg/ml (0.125, 0.250, 0.5, 1.0, 2.0, 4.0, 8.0 and 16 mg/ml) were prepared in DMSO which was then filtered through membrane filter. The extracts were mixed thoroughly with 14 ml of autoclaved SDA medium and poured into sterile petriplates and were allowed to solidify. Inoculum suspensions (10 µl) of various microbial isolates were seeded on individual agar plates of SDA medium. Growth control was prepared by inoculating 10 µl of each culture suspension on 15 ml SDA medium without any extract or solvent (drug-free medium). Solvent control was prepared by pouring 1ml of DMSO to 14 ml of SDA medium accordingly, followed by seeding of cultures. The

plates were allowed to diffuse for 1h at room temperature and incubated at 25 °C for 48h. Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC), was determined as the lowest concentration of antimicrobial agent that inhibited the visible growth of a microorganism after proper incubation.

Statistical analysis

All the analysis were carried out in triplicates and expressed as mean \pm SD. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) were performed using the one-way analysis of variance. Significant differences between means were determined by Duncan's multiple range tests. P values less than 0.05 were considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

The antifungal activity of different extracts including *n*-hexane, chloroform, ethyl acetate, methanol and aqueous extracts of *in vitro* and *in vivo* grown *Aloe vera* L. whole leaf and inner gel were determined by disc diffusion assay. Subsequently the detection of minimum inhibitory concentrations (MIC) was also done in current study. The results found are explained as further.

Assessment of antifungal activities

Antifungal potentials were determined to study the efficacy of *in vivo* and *in vitro* regenerated *Aloe vera* L. whole leaf and inner gel extracts. Total 6 clinically significant fungal strains including *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Aspergillus fumigatus*, *Penicillium digitatum*, *Candida albicans* and *Candida utilis* were used for this task. All the strains tested were showing measurable zone of inhibition.

As shown in the Table 1 – 4, the standard positive control depicted inhibition diameter ranging from 19.80 ± 0.63 mm to 28.10 ± 0.15 mm (Ketoconazole 100 μ g/disc), 20.24 ± 0.71 mm to 31.02 ± 0.28 mm (Fluconazole 100 μ g/disc), against the tested organisms.

All the extracts except aqueous extracts of whole leaf and inner gel samples were showing significant antifungal activities in disc diffusion assay against most of the microbial genre tested. Among all the samples ethyl acetate extracts were showing the larger zone of inhibition compared to other extract, as shown in the Table 1 – 4. Methanol, Chloroform and then *n*-hexane extracts were also showing the significant inhibition zone against the

pathogens tested while aqueous extracts were totally unable to inhibit any of the pathogens tested (Table 1 – 4).

All the fungal strains including *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Aspergillus fumigatus*, *Penicillium digitatum*, *Candida albicans* and *Candida utilis*, tested with various extracts of different samples including whole leaf and inner gel extracts of *in vivo* and *in vitro* regenerated *Aloe vera* L., were showing the significant sensitivity against standard antibiotics as well as all the extracts of *in vivo* and *in vitro* regenerated *Aloe vera* L. whole leaf and inner gel (Table 1 – 4).

In the present investigation all the pathogens tested were showing varying degree of inhibition with different extracts including *n*-hexane, chloroform, ethyl acetate, methanol and aqueous extracts of *in vivo* and *in vitro* regenerated *Aloe vera* L. whole leaf and inner gel. Among all the extracts, ethyl acetate extracts were showing the strong inhibitory activity towards all the pathogens tested, in other words the ethyl acetate extracts were depicted the higher degree of antifungal activities and when we compare among the different samples of *Aloe vera* L. including *in vitro* grown whole leaf and only gel as well as *in vivo* grown whole leaf and only gel, the *in vitro* regenerated only gel extracts were showing the highest degree of inhibition (Table 1 – 4).

Overall, from all the results (Table 1 – 4) it can be concluded that *Aloe vera* L. has a significant antimicrobial activity against the fungal strains of human health significance and can be used as the antifungal remedies in the preparation of antimicrobial drugs/medicines.

Minimum inhibitory concentrations (MIC)

MIC was determined for *n*-hexane, chloroform, ethyl acetate, methanol and aqueous extracts of leaves of *in vivo* and *in vitro* regenerated *Aloe vera* L. whole leaf and inner gel samples, by Agar Dilution method (Table 5 – 8). Ethyl acetate extracts had lowest MIC, followed by methanol, chloroform and *n*-hexane extracts, whereas aqueous extracts were not tested for their MIC because they were unable to inhibit any of the pathogens tested in disc diffusion method done in initial part of this study.

For the samples of *in vitro* regenerated *Aloe vera* L. whole leaf extracts (Table 5), the *n*-hexane extract was showing MIC of 4.0 mg/ml. against *Candida albicans* and *Candida utilis*. Whereas MIC of 8.0 mg/ml. against *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Aspergillus*

fumigatus and *Penicillium digitatum*. The chloroform extract showed MIC of 4.0 mg/ml. against *Aspergillus flavus*, *Penicillium digitatum*, *Candida albicans* and *Candida utilis* while *Aspergillus niger* and *Aspergillus fumigatus* were inhibited at 8.0 mg/ml. in chloroform extract of *in vitro* regenerated *Aloe vera* L. whole leaf samples. The ethyl acetate extract was showing MIC of 0.1 mg/ml. against *Candida albicans* and *Candida utilis*. *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus* and *Penicillium digitatum* were inhibited at a MIC of 2.0 mg/ml. MIC of 4.0 mg/ml. was detected against *Aspergillus fumigatus* in ethyl acetate extract of *in vitro* regenerated *Aloe vera* L. whole leaf samples. Methanol extract of *in vitro* regenerated *Aloe vera* L. whole leaf samples were showing the MIC of 2.0 mg/ml. against *Penicillium digitatum*, *Candida albicans* and *Candida utilis* whereas the growth of *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus* and *Aspergillus fumigatus* were inhibited at MIC of 4.0 mg/ml. (Table 5).

As shown in Table 6, among the samples of *in vitro* regenerated *Aloe vera* L. only gel extracts examined, the MIC of *n*-hexane extract was found 2.0 mg/ml. against the growth of *Candida albicans* and *Candida utilis*. The growth of *Aspergillus flavus* and *Aspergillus fumigatus* were inhibited at the MIC of 4.0 mg/ml. Consequently, MIC of 8.0mg/ml. were found to inhibit the growth of *Aspergillus niger* and *Penicillium digitatum*. Chloroform extract of *in vitro* regenerated *Aloe vera* L. only gel samples were showing the MIC of 1.0 mg/ml. against the growth of *Candida albicans* and *Candida utilis* followed by the MIC of 2.0 mg/ml. against *Aspergillus flavus* and *Aspergillus fumigatus*. The growth of *Aspergillus niger* and *Penicillium digitatum* were found to inhibit at the MIC of 4.0 mg/ml. Ethyl acetate extract of *in vitro* regenerated *Aloe vera* L. only gel samples showed MIC of 0.125 mg/ml. against *Candida albicans*. Growth of *Candida utilis* was inhibited at MIC of 0.250 mg/ml., followed by *Aspergillus flavus* and *Aspergillus fumigatus* that showed MIC of 0.5 mg/ml. *Penicillium digitatum* was inhibited at 1.0 mg/ml in ethyl acetate extract of *in vitro* regenerated *Aloe vera* L. only gel samples. MIC of 2.0 mg/ml. was found against the growth of *Aspergillus niger*. Methanol extracts were found to inhibit the growth of *Candida albicans* and *Candida utilis* at the MIC of 0.250 mg/ml. At the same time MIC of 1.0 mg/ml. was found to inhibit the growth of *Aspergillus flavus* and *Aspergillus fumigatus*, followed by MIC of 2.0 mg/ml. which was found to prevent the growth of *Aspergillus niger* and *Penicillium digitatum*. (Table 6).

As shown in the Table 7, *n*-hexane extract of *in vivo* grown *Aloe vera* L. whole leaf extract was depicted the MIC of 8.0mg/ml. against the growth of *Penicillium digitatum*, *Candida*

albicans and *Candida utilis*. The growth of *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus* and *Aspergillus fumigatus* were found to inhibit at the MIC of 16.0 mg/ml. The chloroform extract of *in vivo* grown *Aloe vera* L. whole leaf samples were detected to inhibit the growth of *Aspergillus flavus*, *Penicillium digitatum*, *Candida albicans* and *Candida utilis* at the MIC of 8.0 mg/ml., whereas *Aspergillus niger* and *Aspergillus fumigatus* were found to inhibit at the MIC of 16.0 mg/ml. Ethyl acetate extract of *in vivo* grown *Aloe vera* L. whole leaf samples were showing the MIC of 4.0 mg/ml against *Penicillium digitatum*, *Candida albicans* and *Candida utilis* followed by *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus* and *Aspergillus fumigatus* that showed MIC of 8.0 mg/ml. in ethyl acetate extract of *in vivo* grown *Aloe vera* L. whole leaf samples. Methanol extract of *in vivo* grown *Aloe vera* L. whole leaf samples were found to show MIC of 4.0 mg/ml. against the growth of *Candida albicans* and *Candida utilis*. The growth of *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Aspergillus fumigatus* and *Penicillium digitatum* were found to inhibit at MIC of 8.0 mg/ml (Table 7).

Result in Table 8 has shown that among the samples of *in vivo* grown *Aloe vera* L. only gel, *n*-hexane extracts were depicted the MIC of 8.0 mg/ml. against the growth of *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Penicillium digitatum*, *Candida albicans* and *Candida utilis*. Whereas the MIC of 16.0 mg/ml. found to inhibit the growth of *Aspergillus fumigatus* by *n*-hexane extract of *in vivo* grown *Aloe vera* L. only gel samples. The chloroform extracts of *in vivo* grown *Aloe vera* L. only gel sample was showing the MIC of 4.0 mg/ml. against *Candida albicans*. At the same time MIC of 8.0 mg/ml. was found to prevent the growth of *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Penicillium digitatum* and *Candida utilis*, followed by the MIC of 16.0 mg/ml. which was able to prevent the growth of *Aspergillus fumigatus*. Ethyl acetate extract of *in vivo* grown *Aloe vera* L. only gel inhibited *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Penicillium digitatum*, *Candida albicans* and *Candida utilis* at MIC of 4.0 mg/ml, whereas MIC of 8.0 mg/ml was found against *Aspergillus fumigatus* with the ethyl acetate extract of *in vivo* grown *Aloe vera* L. only gel samples. Simultaneously methanol extract of *in vivo* grown *Aloe vera* L. only gel samples were found to show MIC of 4.0 mg/ml against the growth of *Aspergillus flavus*, *Candida albicans* and *Candida utilis*. Subsequently the growth of *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus fumigatus* and *Penicillium digitatum* were found to inhibit at the MIC of 8.0 mg/ml (Table 8).

All the fungal pathogens of clinical significance tested including *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Aspergillus fumigatus*, *Penicillium digitatum*, *Candida albicans* and

Candida utilis were showing their minimum inhibitory concentrations (MIC) against serial 2-fold dilution prepared from the *in vivo* grown and *in vitro* regenerated *Aloe vera* L. whole leaf and only gel samples. These results depicted that *Aloe vera* L. has a good quality of antifungal activities and can be used in the preparation of antimicrobial agents.

Table 1: Antifungal activity of *in vitro* regenerated *Aloe vera* L. whole leaf extracts by disc diffusion method (zone of inhibition in mm at 100 µg/disc).

S.No.	Microorganisms (Pathogens)	<i>n</i> -Hexane	Chloroform	Ethyl Acetate	Methanol	Aqueous	Ketoconazole	Fluconazole
1	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	10.56 ± 0.16	12.49 ± 0.86	14.23 ± 0.52	12.73 ± 0.02	NI	21.57 ± 1.06	25.62 ± 0.82
2	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	11.43 ± 0.83	14.30 ± 0.12	17.04 ± 0.62	15.20 ± 0.18	NI	22.05 ± 0.25	29.30 ± 0.43
3	<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	09.35 ± 0.82	10.52 ± 0.43	14.48 ± 1.19	11.57 ± 0.04	NI	19.80 ± 0.63	20.24 ± 0.71
4	<i>Penicillium digitatum</i>	10.69 ± 1.01	10.91 ± 0.92	16.33 ± 0.36	14.65 ± 0.58	NI	23.62 ± 0.33	24.53 ± 0.06
5	<i>Candida albicans</i>	12.57 ± 0.06	16.76 ± 0.18	19.24 ± 0.02	16.19 ± 0.24	NI	28.10 ± 0.15	31.02 ± 0.28
6	<i>Candida utilis</i>	12.74 ± 0.82	13.47 ± 0.36	17.68 ± 0.42	14.55 ± 0.06	NI	26.03 ± 0.76	29.43 ± 0.37

The values are given as Mean ± SD of triplicates

The concentration of extracts used was 100 µg/disc

* Inhibitory zone in mm, including diameter of disc (5.0 mm)

NI - No Inhibition

Table 2: Antifungal activity of *in vitro* regenerated *Aloe vera* L. only gel extracts by disc diffusion method (zone of inhibition in mm at 100 µg/disc).

S.No.	Microorganisms (Pathogens)	<i>n</i> -Hexane	Chloroform	Ethyl Acetate	Methanol	Aqueous	Ketoconazole	Fluconazole
1	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	12.37 ± 0.43	15.46 ± 0.21	19.57 ± 1.57	16.72 ± 1.15	NI	21.57 ± 1.06	25.62 ± 0.82
2	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	16.18 ± 0.56	18.31 ± 0.20	23.48 ± 0.83	19.06 ± 0.42	NI	22.05 ± 0.25	29.30 ± 0.43
3	<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	12.72 ± 0.82	13.62 ± 0.47	18.33 ± 0.02	15.46 ± 0.29	NI	19.80 ± 0.63	20.24 ± 0.71
4	<i>Penicillium digitatum</i>	14.34 ± 0.24	15.06 ± 0.90	22.20 ± 0.12	18.67 ± 0.36	NI	23.62 ± 0.33	24.53 ± 0.06
5	<i>Candida albicans</i>	17.04 ± 1.47	18.49 ± 0.02	25.65 ± 0.18	20.33 ± 0.50	NI	28.10 ± 0.15	31.02 ± 0.28
6	<i>Candida utilis</i>	16.39 ± 0.32	18.76 ± 0.06	24.43 ± 0.10	19.50 ± 0.36	NI	26.03 ± 0.76	29.43 ± 0.37

The values are given as Mean ± SD of triplicates

The concentration of extracts used was 100 µg/disc

* Inhibitory zone in mm, including diameter of disc (5.0 mm)

NI - No Inhibition

Table 3: Antifungal activity of *in vivo* grown *Aloe vera* L. whole leaf extracts by disc diffusion method (zone of inhibition in mm at 100 µg/disc).

S.No.	Microorganisms (Pathogens)	<i>n</i> -Hexane	Chloroform	Ethyl Acetate	Methanol	Aqueous	Ketoconazole	Fluconazole
1	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	08.42 ± 0.76	09.26 ± 0.24	11.86 ± 0.08	10.28 ± 0.60	NI	21.57 ± 1.06	25.62 ± 0.82
2	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	08.37 ± 0.42	11.72 ± 0.57	14.28 ± 0.20	12.02 ± 0.29	NI	22.05 ± 0.25	29.30 ± 0.43
3	<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	08.02 ± 0.16	08.57 ± 0.32	12.50 ± 0.05	09.74 ± 1.18	NI	19.80 ± 0.63	20.24 ± 0.71
4	<i>Penicillium digitatum</i>	08.24 ± 0.62	09.28 ± 0.17	13.53 ± 0.84	11.29 ± 0.12	NI	23.62 ± 0.33	24.53 ± 0.06
5	<i>Candida albicans</i>	11.84 ± 0.35	12.31 ± 0.22	17.08 ± 0.47	13.36 ± 0.28	NI	28.10 ± 0.15	31.02 ± 0.28
6	<i>Candida utilis</i>	11.03 ± 0.27	11.76 ± 0.28	15.54 ± 0.05	12.24 ± 0.43	NI	26.03 ± 0.76	29.43 ± 0.37

The values are given as Mean ± SD of triplicates

The concentration of extracts used was 100 µg/disc

* Inhibitory zone in mm, including diameter of disc (5.0 mm)

NI - No Inhibition

Table 4: Antifungal activity of *in vivo* grown *Aloe vera* L. only gel extracts by disc diffusion method (zone of inhibition in mm at 100 µg/disc)

S.No.	Microorganisms (Pathogens)	<i>n</i> -Hexane	Chloroform	Ethyl Acetate	Methanol	Aqueous	Ketoconazole	Fluconazole
1	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	09.36 ± 0.62	10.43 ± 0.05	12.24 ± 0.40	11.20 ± 0.27	NI	21.57 ± 1.06	25.62 ± 0.82
2	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	08.43 ± 0.33	12.08 ± 0.19	16.31 ± 0.70	13.82 ± 0.37	NI	22.05 ± 0.25	29.30 ± 0.43
3	<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	08.56 ± 0.02	09.62 ± 0.82	13.57 ± 0.21	10.18 ± 0.43	NI	19.80 ± 0.63	20.24 ± 0.71
4	<i>Penicillium digitatum</i>	08.24 ± 0.36	09.76 ± 0.20	15.39 ± 0.15	12.54 ± 0.17	NI	23.62 ± 0.33	24.53 ± 0.06
5	<i>Candida albicans</i>	12.05 ± 0.20	13.55 ± 1.39	18.04 ± 0.42	15.62 ± 0.16	NI	28.10 ± 0.15	31.02 ± 0.28
6	<i>Candida utilis</i>	11.24 ± 0.43	12.37 ± 0.76	16.48 ± 0.62	13.74 ± 0.39	NI	26.03 ± 0.76	29.43 ± 0.37

The values are given as Mean ± SD of triplicates

The concentration of extracts used was 100 µg/disc

* Inhibitory zone in mm, including diameter of disc (5.0 mm)

NI - No Inhibition

Table 5: Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of *in vitro* regenerated *Aloe vera* L. whole leaf extracts.

S.No.	Microorganisms (Pathogens)	MIC (mg/ml.)				
		<i>n</i> -Hexane	Chloroform	Ethyl Acetate	Methanol	Aqueous
1	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	8.0	8.0	2.0	4.0	NT
2	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	8.0	4.0	2.0	4.0	NT
3	<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	8.0	8.0	4.0	4.0	NT
4	<i>Penicillium digitatum</i>	8.0	4.0	2.0	2.0	NT
5	<i>Candida albicans</i>	4.0	4.0	1.0	2.0	NT
6	<i>Candida utilis</i>	4.0	4.0	1.0	2.0	NT

NT - Not Tested

Table 6: Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of *in vitro* regenerated *Aloe vera* L. only gel extracts.

S.No.	Microorganisms (Pathogens)	MIC (mg/ml.)				
		<i>n</i> -Hexane	Chloroform	Ethyl Acetate	Methanol	Aqueous
1	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	8.0	4.0	2.0	2.0	NT
2	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	4.0	2.0	0.5	1.0	NT
3	<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	4.0	2.0	0.5	1.0	NT
4	<i>Penicillium digitatum</i>	8.0	4.0	1.0	2.0	NT
5	<i>Candida albicans</i>	2.0	1.0	0.125	0.250	NT
6	<i>Candida utilis</i>	2.0	1.0	0.250	0.250	NT

NT - Not Tested

Table 7: Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of *in vivo* grown *Aloe vera* L. whole leaf extracts.

S.No.	Microorganisms (Pathogens)	MIC (mg/ml.)				
		<i>n</i> -Hexane	Chloroform	Ethyl Acetate	Methanol	Aqueous
1	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	16.0	16.0	8.0	8.0	NT
2	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	16.0	8.0	8.0	8.0	NT
3	<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	16.0	16.0	8.0	8.0	NT
4	<i>Penicillium digitatum</i>	8.0	8.0	4.0	8.0	NT
5	<i>Candida albicans</i>	8.0	8.0	4.0	4.0	NT
6	<i>Candida utilis</i>	8.0	8.0	4.0	4.0	NT

NT - Not Tested

Table 8: Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of *in vivo* grown *Aloe vera* L. only gel extracts.

S.No.	Microorganisms (Pathogens)	MIC (mg/ml.)				
		<i>n</i> -Hexane	Chloroform	Ethyl Acetate	Methanol	Aqueous
1	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	8.0	8.0	4.0	8.0	NT
2	<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	8.0	8.0	4.0	4.0	NT
3	<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	16.0	16.0	8.0	8.0	NT
4	<i>Penicillium digitatum</i>	8.0	8.0	4.0	8.0	NT
5	<i>Candida albicans</i>	8.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	NT
6	<i>Candida utilis</i>	8.0	8.0	4.0	4.0	NT

NT - Not Tested

DISCUSSION

Interestingly, this study recorded a notable susceptibility of the resistant strains, to all the extracts including whole leaf and inner gel extracts from *in vitro* and *in vivo* grown *Aloe vera* L., suggesting that components contained in that particular extracts may provide an alternate strategy for combating these organisms and could improve treatment of infections caused by these organisms. The remarkable findings of this study are that *Aloe vera* L. extracts are potentially effective against fungi.

Aloe vera L. gel extracts seemed to contain higher amounts antifungal components as compared to whole leaf extracts. When compared between *in vitro* regenerated *Aloe vera* L. and *in vivo* grown *Aloe vera* L., it was found that *in vitro* regenerated plants were showing greater antifungal activities.

The present observations are in agreement with the reports of Tatli *et al.*,^[8] who showed that saponin was responsible for significant antifungal activity by weakening the virulence of *C. albicans* and killing fungi by destroying their cell membranes.^[9] All the solvent extracts were showing the different degree of inhibition against all the fungal strains tested.

MIC results obtained in the present study showed that ethyl acetate extracts of *in vitro* and *in vivo* grown *Aloe vera* L. whole leaf and inner gel had greater antifungal activities, as ethyl acetate extracts required the lesser concentrations to inhibit the pathogens followed by methanol, chloroform and *n*-hexane extracts, while aqueous extracts were found unable to inhibit any of the pathogens tested. The results of this study are in accordance with the findings of Aliero *et al.*, on *S. hyacinthoides*.^[10]

The outcomes of the present study also reflected the presence of potent phytochemicals in solvent extracts of whole leaf and inner gel of *Aloe vera* L. which could be responsible for its antimicrobial activity.^[11,12,13,14] Therefore, in view of these results, the ability of the extracts to inhibit the growth of several fungal species is an indication of the broad-spectrum antifungal potential of *Aloe vera* L. which makes the plant a candidate for bio-prospecting for antifungal drugs.

Therefore, several studies by different workers including results and observations of the current investigation strongly supports that the active components present in *Aloe vera* L. possesses strong antifungal potentials.

CONCLUSION

In present investigation assessment of antifungal activities of *in vivo* and *in vitro* regenerated *Aloe vera* L. leaf gel and whole leaf extracts was attempted. The antifungal activity of different extracts of *Aloe vera* L. (both *in vivo* grown and *in vitro* regenerated) whole leaf and inner gel were tested against number of clinically important fungal strains related to human health including *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Aspergillus fumigatus*, *Penicillium digitatum*, *Candida albicans* and *Candida utilis* by disc diffusion assay. Ethyle acetate extracts were found to be more potent in inhibiting all the fungal strains tested, other extracts including methanol, chloroform and *n*-Hexane were also showing the significant zone of inhibition except the aqueous extract, which was unable to inhibit any fungal strain. Detection of minimum inhibitory concentrations (MIC) was also done. MIC results obtained in the present study showed that ethyl acetate extracts of *in vitro* and *in vivo* grown *Aloe vera* L. whole leaf and inner gel had greater antifungal activities, as ethyl acetate extracts required the lesser concentrations to inhibit the fungal pathogens followed by methanol, chloroform and *n*-hexane extracts, while aqueous extracts were found unable to inhibit any of the fungal pathogens tested. That's why it can be concluded that *Aloe vera* L. has a significant potential against fungal strains of human health significance.

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